

FEATURES OF MORPHO-PHYSIOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL SPECIALIZATION OF HELMINTHS

¹Fotima Sharipovna Nazarova, ²Nargiza Eshmamatovna Djumanova, ³Barchinoy
Kamolovna Murodullayeva

^{1,2} Department of Medical Biology and Genetics, Samarkand State Medical Institute

³ Student of Samarqand state medical university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7699830>

Abstract. *In the period of evolutionary development, according to the morphological structure of the body of helminths, the father adapted to live a parasitic life, especially to digest substances by the anaerobic way. Biochemical characteristics of adaptation to living as an anaerobic organism is the peculiarity of substance and energy metabolism in helminths. The increase in the activity of certain enzyme systems during adulthood, rapid growth, development, and rapid provision of protein biosynthesis to leave many offspring are the main signs of adaptation of helminths to parasitic life.*

Keywords: *helminth, larvocystius, micro-trichia, Krebs chain, anaerobes, mitochondria, ATP synthesis.*

The purpose of the research: to study the adaptation of helminths to parasitic life and the peculiarities of their morpho-physiological and biochemical specialization in the host organism.

Research materials and results: Fasciola hepatica, Dicrocoelium lanceatum species of trematode (Trematoda) class of flatworms do not have a body head, it is filled with cells of parenchyma tissue. The digestive system consists of a mouth opening from the center of the oral cavity, a pharynx, a short esophagus, and two large intestines ending with a caecum. Close the back exit (anal) hole. It is mainly fed with blood, tissue, intercellular juices, digested nutrients are absorbed directly from the intestine into the parenchyma cells. Undigested food residues are excreted through the mouth. Cestodes belong to parenchymatous animals, similar to trematodes. The body consists of a head (scolex), neck and joints, and its surface is a tegument covered with microvilli - microtrichia of the inner epithelial tissue of the intestine of highly structured animals. In them, digestive enzymes belonging to the group of hydrolytic phosphatases are active and perform the function of food digesting-absorbing azo. Because in Cestodes, the digestive, respiratory, and circulatory systems of the azole are not clearly developed.

The host's organism clings to the villi of the inside of the host's body through the variously developed suckers and loops on the head (scolex), and absorbs ready-made nutrients (monosaccharides, amino acids, fatty acids, glycerin, vitamins, hormones, mineral salts and other metabolites) through the microtrichia covering its body. feeds, because it lives in conditions of oxygen deficiency, it digests them through anaerobic oxidation. (Benedictov I. I, 1982, Urolov M.U., 1990, 1991). One of the physiological-biochemical characteristics of helminths to lead a parasitic life, especially to an intermediate or main host organism, is their infectious (invasive) period - the period when mobile larvae hatch from eggs (oncospheres) or larval cysts.

The invasion period of the parasites entering the host's body through nutrition changes from the "quiet" state to the "development" period by means of an "explosion". It is affected by the temperature of the internal environment of the living organism, enzymes and other bioactive factors. First of all, under the normalized temperature, the concentration of HCO₃ ions increases,

and the egg (oncosphere) is pushed into the internal environment through the larval cyst membrane, acting as a special receptor on the receptors of the embryo or larvae of the helminth. As a result, the biosynthesis of special juices (enzymes) such as chitinase, leucine-aminopentidase, esterase begins. In turn, under the action of enzymes, the shell of the helminth egg, the cyst (bag) of the invasion larva dissolves, and the invasion larva comes out, settles in the tissues of the internal environment of the host, starts postembryonic or imaginal development, feeds, differentiates, and the adult larva (larvocyst) turns into a parasitic helminth stage. It is a biochemical description of adaptation to life as an anaerobic organism, and it is a peculiarity of substance and energy metabolism in helminths. In particular, a strong increase in carbon water metabolism, a variety of the end products of metabolism, an increase in the activity of some enzyme systems with the periods of adulthood, and a rapid increase in the biosynthesis of proteins for rapid growth, development and leaving many offspring are the main signs of adaptation of helminths to a parasitic lifestyle.

Cell mitochondria, which ensure the biological oxidation of consumed ready-made nutrients in the "respiratory chain", are present in the cells of all parts of the body of trematodes (for example, the liver worm *Fasciola hepatica*), and in other nematodes (for example, the human *Ascaris lumbricoides*), mainly in the contractile muscle tissue. It is found in large quantities in cells, and in cestodes (for example, human and rat worm - *Hymenolepis diminuta*) in small quantities in cells in the sarcoplasm of muscle fibers. Accordingly, in helminths it was found that all the enzymes in the Krebs chain are present, but their activity is very low. The conversion of fumarate into succinic acid in the presence of HAD,H is the most important sign of adaptation of helminths to anaerobic conditions due to the activity of fumarate reductase enzyme in this chain. Therefore, the malate (malic acid) formed in the parasite's cytoplasm is the substrate for all oxidation-reduction reactions in the mitochondria. Enzymes such as succinate dehydrogenase, alpha-ketoglutarate dehydrogenase, fumarase, and isocitrate dehydrogenase are also found in mitochondria. This ensures the formation of amber (succinate), propionate, acetate and lactic acid as end products of metabolism. Only in nematodes, lactate dehydrogenase enzyme is found outside the mitochondrion, therefore only lactic acid is present in their metabolites. Synthesis of ATF is carried out in mitochondria by biochemical changes due to the conversion of fumarate to succinic acid through the flavoprotein system.

Conclusion: the metabolism in helminths, including the strong increase in carbon water metabolism, the diversity of the end products of metabolism, the number of activities of some enzyme systems with the periods of adulthood, and the rapid maintenance of the biosynthesis of proteins for rapid growth, development and leaving a large number of offspring are the adaptations of helminths to parasitic life are the main signs.

REFERENCES

1. Венчиков А.И. Физиологически активные количества микроэлементов как биотический фактор. //Рига, 2019,- с.571-575.
2. Назарова Ф,Ш., Маткаримова Г.М. Морфо – физиологические и биохимические приспособления гельминтов.
3. Назаров Ш.Н., Риш,М.А., Шукуров Д. Использование химического анализа шерсти при крупномасштабном биогеохимическом районировании и дифференциальном применении микроэлементов в животноводстве.//№7.с.32-34.

4. Назаров Ш.Н. Полярографическое определение цинка в растительном материале. Изд. «Фан», Ташкент, 2009, с.179.
5. Риш. М.А., Назаров Ш.Н. Содержание некоторых микроэлементов в шерсти каракульских овец различной окраски. //М.2013.№9.с.49-54.
6. Назарова Ф.Ш., Худойбердиева Г., Джуманова Н.Э. Биохимический сравнительный анализ экологического состава фитонематод.
7. Назарова Ф. Ш., Джуманова Н. Э. Использование бентонита азкамарского месторождения для балансировки минерального питания // Академические исследования в области педагогических наук. – 2021. – Вып. 2. – № 9. – С. 672-679.
8. Назарова Ф.С., Джуманова Н.Е. Волосно-шерстный покров как индикаторы загрязнения окружающей среды техногенными и геохимическими источниками // Тематический журнал микробиологии. – 2022. – Вып. 6. – №1.
9. Назарова Ф.С., Джуманова Н.Е., Ташмаматов Б.Н., Ш. О. Коржавов. Экологическая группировка фитонематод. Проблемы биологии и медицины. - 2020. № 6. Том 124. - С. 258-261.
10. Назарова Ф.Ш., Джуманова Н.Е. Биологическая роль микроэлементов и их содержание в эпидермальных образованиях. Экономика и общество.1-2 (92).2022. стр. 94-103
11. Тошмаматов Б.Н. и соавт. Макроскопическая структура илеоцекального лоскута у кроликов //Международная научно-практическая конференция «Мировая наука. – РОСТ, 2017. – С. 5. – № 5. – С. 58-59.
12. Тошмаматов Б.Н. и соавт. Макроскопическая структура илеоцекального отверстия кркс и кроликов в постнатальном онтогенезе //Международная научно-практическая конференция «Мировая наука. – РОСТ, 2018. – № 3. – № 5. – С. 53- С.
13. Тошмаматов Б.Н., Тешаев Ш.Дж., Худойбердиев Д.К. Последствия полипрагмазии противовоспалительными препаратами на морфологию стенки желудка Проблемы биологии и медицины 2022, №1 (134) С.157-164
14. Тошмаматов Б.Н., Тешаев Ш. Дж., Худойбердиев Д.К., Морфологическая структура слизистой оболочки желудка при полипрагмазии противовоспалительными препаратами Среднеевропейский научный бюллетень Том 20, январь 2022 г., страницы 32-38
15. Тошмаматов Б.Н., Тешаев Ш. J. Изменение морфологической структуры слизистой оболочки при полипрагмазии. (2021). Американский журнал медицинских наук и фармацевтических исследований, 3 (08), 51–57.
16. Ташмаматов Б.Н. Морфометрические показатели слизистой желудка при полипрагмазии на противовоспалительных препаратах 9 (47) 2022. Новый день в медицине. С.187-195
17. Тошмаматов Б. Н. и др. Макроскопическое строение илеоцекальной заслонки у кроликов. //International Scientific and Practical Conference World science. – ROST, 2017. – Т. 5. – №. 5. – С. 58-59.
18. Тошмаматов Б. Н. и др. Макроскопическое строение илеоцекального отверстия у кроликов и крыс в постнатальном онтогенезе //International Scientific and Practical Conference World science. – ROST, 2018. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 53-54.

19. Худайбердиева Г. А., Назарова Ф. Ш., Джуманова Н. Э. Сравнительный анализ экологического состава фитонематод //Форум молодых ученых. – 2021. – №. 4. – С. 381-385.
20. Dzhumanova N. E., Nazarova F. S. PROBABLE NEGATIVE IMPACT OF GENETICALLY MODIFIED PRODUCTS ON HUMAN HEALTH //Thematics Journal of Botany. – 2022. – Т. 6. – №. 1.
21. Nazarova F. S., Dzhumanova N. E. HAIR AND WOOL AS INDICATORS OF ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION BY MAN-MADE AND GEOCHEMICAL SOURCES //Thematics Journal of Microbiology. – 2022. – Т. 6. – №. 1.
22. Sharipovna N. F. et al. BIOLOGICAL ROLE OF MICROELEMENTS AND THEIR CONTENT IN EPIDERMAL FORMATIONS //European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine. – 2021. – Т. 8. – №. 2. – С. 1675-1687.